

Quantum Entropy and Energy States Part II

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 23, 2022

In this note we wish to examine three ideas. First we consider the case of $W(x,t) = \sum_n \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$ ((1)) (for $n=0,1$ as an example) and note that the von Neumann entropy is 0 for such a state. This is pointed out in (1) together with the fact that there exists a von Neumann density operator $\exp(-H/T)$ (H =Hamiltonian operator) which yields the same result as Shannon's entropy S using $P(e_i)$ if one uses $dQ/T = \sum_n \ln dP(e_n)/T = dS$. It seems then that there is a contradiction if the usual von Neumann entropy is 0 yet using a density operator $= \exp(-H/T)$ yields nonzero results. A resolution is suggested in (2) which deals with information theory and we see if it applies to ((1)).

Secondly, we consider the Shannon's form $P(e) \ln(P(e))$ in more detail. In Part I and in previous notes we argued that \ln ensures that $S = S_1 + S_2$ if one has two systems. We also argued that $dE = \sum_n \ln dP(e_n) = T dS$ if $dW_{\text{work}} = 0$. In this note, we argue that a stronger idea may be at work, namely the idea that $E_{\text{ave}} = \sum_n \ln P(e_n/T)$ and TS are essentially the same function except for a function of T . This approach may be used to show that \ln is the function associated with entropy.

Finally, we note as in Part I that when using either the von Neumann approach or Shannon's entropy one must know which probabilities to use. For a system with energy levels e_n , $P(n) = P(e_n/T)$ is an immediate candidate, but there may be more probabilities in the system related to a particle jumping from one e_i to another. In such a case, if one uses these probabilities and then sums over some of them leaving only $P(e_n/T)$, the form of entropy changes from that of Shannon's form. (Originally, however, Shannon's form is used before summing.)

Von Neumann Entropy

For a system $W(x,t) = \sum_n \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$ ((1)) von Neumann's entropy is defined in (2) by a density matrix:

$$D_{ij} = a_i^* a_j \quad ((2)) \quad \text{where} \quad S = - \text{Trace} (D \ln (D)) \quad ((3))$$

If one diagonalizes D and finds the eigenvalues $\{b_i\}$ then S has the mathematical form of Shannon's entropy, but the former uses eigenvalues of a matrix and the latter eigenvalues of D i.e.

$$S_{\text{von Neumann}} = - \sum_i b_i \ln(b_i) \quad \text{where } b_i \text{ is an eigenvalue of } D.$$

If $DD=D$ one has a pure state and $S_{\text{von Neumann}} = 0$ i.e. $\text{Tr}(D \ln(D)) = \text{Tr}(D \ln(DD)) = 2 \text{Tr}(D \ln D) = 0$. Consider a two energy level example for ((1)) with $a_1 = \sqrt{b}$ and $a_2 = \sqrt{1-b}$. Then:

$$D = \begin{vmatrix} b & \sqrt{b}\sqrt{1-b} \\ \sqrt{b}\sqrt{1-b} & 1-b \end{vmatrix} \quad ((4))$$

$DD = D$ for ((4)) so von Neumann's entropy is 0.

It seems, however, that von Neumann's density is also defined as $\exp(-H/T)$ where H is the Hamiltonian operator with eigenstates $|e_i\rangle$ and eigenvalues e_i and T temperature (1). In such a case the density operator is diagonal for ((1)) i.e.

$$D = \begin{vmatrix} \exp(-e_i/T)/C(T, e_1, e_2) & 0 \\ 0 & \exp(-e_i/T)/C(e_1, e_2, T) \end{vmatrix} \quad ((5))$$

Thus von Neumann's entropy ((5)) is the same as :

$$\text{Shannon's } S = - \sum \text{over } n \ P(e_n) \ln(P(e_n)) \quad \text{where } P(e_n) = \exp(-e_n/T) / C(e_1, e_2, T) \quad ((6))$$

This has been noted in (1) together with the idea that ((4)) represents 0 von Neumann entropy. Thus there seems to be a contradiction, entropy for the same system is 0 and not zero. In (3) a resolution is suggested based on information theory, namely to only use diagonal elements in the D matrix. In such a case ((4)) becomes:

$$D = \begin{vmatrix} b & 0 \\ 0 & 1-b \end{vmatrix} \quad ((6))$$

And S von Neumann = - { $b \ln(b) + (1-b) \ln(1-b)$ } Also $E_{ave} = be_1 + (1-b)e_2$

To bring T into the picture, one may use the suggestion of (1) namely: $dQ/T = dS$. One may note that the approach of ((6)) is to consider that in terms of probabilities of energy one does not have an operator mixing states i.e. $\langle e_i | B | e_j \rangle$. In other words ((6)) seems to be almost classical.

Ln Form of Entropy

In Part I and previous notes, we argued that the form $S = -\sum \text{over } n \ P(e_n) \ln(P(e_n))$ is linear i.e. leads to $S = S_1 + S_2$ for $P_1(e_i)P_2(e_j)$. From this we considered $dE = TdS$ with $d\text{Work} = 0$ and found that $\exp(-e_i/T)/C = P(e_i/T)$ is a solution. Here we argue that a stronger idea seems to be at work than just linearity.

First we consider $dE = \sum \text{over } i \ e_i dP(e_i)$ and $S = \sum \text{over } i \ P(e_i)F(P(e_i))$. Then

$$e_i = F(P(e_i)) + P(e_i) dF/dP \quad ((7))$$

((7)) is still quite general, but if one insists that $E_i = F(P(e_i)) + \text{Constant}$ then the first term of ((7)) yields e_i (plus a constant) and PdF/dP must be a constant. In such a case:

$$F(P(e_i)) = \ln(P(e_i)) \quad ((8))$$

Thus Eave and TS are very similar functions differing only by constant which is a function of T. For a quantum system this is not surprising because one varies $dP(e_i)$ if the mechanical parameter (e.g. L =box size for a box with infinite potential walls and $E_n = n^2\pi^2\hbar^2/2mL^2$ constant) is held constant.

Another way to see this result is to consider $P(e_i/T)$ and $dE=dE/dT$ for a change in which $dW_{\text{work}}=0$. If $E = \sum_i e_i P(e_i)$ and TS have the same form up to a constant say $B(T)$ i.e.

$E-TS = B(T)$ ((9)) then:

For $dW_{\text{work}}=0$, $dE/dT = TdS/dT$, but S contains $P(e_i/T)$ so:

$dE/dT = \sum_i e_i dP(e_i/T)/dT$ Imagine $S = - \sum_i P(e_i/T) F(P(e_i/T))$. Then:

$dS/dT = - \sum_i dP(e_i/T)/dT F(P) - P(e_i/T) dF/dP (e_i/T)$

One is again back to the form: $-T F(P(e_i/T)) + T P dF/dP (e_i/T) = e_i + \text{constant}(T)$

If $F = \ln(P(e_i/T))$. Thus the \ln found in the entropy expression does not need to follow only from the argument of linearity. Both in classical statistical mechanics (for an ideal gas) and quantum mechanics one has the form: $E-TS = B(T) = \text{Helmholtz free energy}$ where:

$$B(T) = -T \ln \left\{ \sum_i \exp(-e_i/T) \right\}$$

i.e. $-T \ln(C(T))$ where $C(T)$ is the normalization constant of $\exp(-e_i/T)$ in $P(e_i/T)$. Interestingly, $W(x)$ the wavefunction of an eigenstate $= \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ where $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ is the unnormalized conditional probability $P(p/x)$.

Why does one use TS ? S is a function of $P(e_i/T)$ where T is a parameter with energy units to make e_i/T dimensionless. S is a function of $P(e_i/T)$'s so $\ln(P(e_i/T))$ does not just yield e_i , but e_i/T so one needs the parameter T in front of S to remove T .

Which Probabilities to Choose

Both the von Neumann, modified von Neumann (using only diagonal elements of D) and Shannon's entropy use probabilities, but we argue that one must be careful which probabilities to use. For example, given ((1)), a_n is a probability to be in energy eigenstate n , but $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ (bound state) is $P(x)$ and $P_n(p) = b_n(p)b_n(p)$ where $W_n(x) = \sum_p b_n(p)\exp(ipx)$. Thus there are several probabilities in the picture. $E_{\text{ave}} = \sum_n e_n P(n)$ thus a probability related to state n is needed. It is an assumption that $P(n) = P(e_n/T)$ i.e. that probability only depends on e_n . In Part I we argued that one could use $P(e_n/T)P_n(x)P_n(p)$ in Shannon's entropy yielding:

$$S = -\left\{ \sum_n P(e_n) \ln(P(e_n)) + \sum_n P(e_n) (S_p(n) + S_x) \right\} \quad (9)$$

Here $S_p(n) = -\int dp b_n(p) \ln(b_n(p))$ and $S_x = -\int dx W_n(x) \ln[W_n(x)]$. For a particle in a box with infinite potential walls $S_p(n)$ and S_x is not. If one only thinks in terms of $P(e_i/T)$ then S from (9) is of the Shannon's form with an added piece. Thus it may be possible to change the Shannon entropy form if one only thinks in terms of one probability, the other probabilities leading to extra terms in S .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we point out a contradiction linked to von Neumann's entropy when linked to a single particle two state system. This contradiction is already noted in (1), but we argue that (3) suggests a solution which seems to work. Secondly, we consider reasons other than linearity for S containing $\ln(P(e_i))$. In particular, we argue that $E - TS = C(T)$ which means that E and S have very similar forms with $S = -\sum_n P(e_n) F(P(e_n))$ such that $F(P(e_n)) = -en/T + B(T)$. Finally we note that although von Neumann's density operator and Shannon's entropy use probabilities, one may have to be careful because it is possible that several probabilities affect the problem. In other words if one has particles jumping from one e_i to another, $P(i)$ may not simply be $P(e_i/T)$.

References

1. Abe, S. and Okuyama, S. Similarities Between Quantum Mechanics and Thermodynamics: Entropy, Temperature and Carnot Cycle
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1012.5581.pdf>
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Von_Neumann_entropy
3. Kak, S. The Transactional Nature of Quantum Information
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/0907.2465.pdf>